

Synthesis of *p*-Methoxy Benzyl-*n*-Heptyl-Acetic acid

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Manuscript received 11 November 1975 ; accepted 5 January 1976.

Ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl malonate was prepared from ethyl malonate and anisic chloride. It was then reacted with sodium. *n*-Heptyl bromide was refluxed with the sodio derivative of ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl malonate to produce ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonate. This was hydrolysed and heated to form *p*-methoxy benzyl-*n*-heptyl acetic acid. Its derivatives such as chloride, amide, anilide, *p*-toluidide, methyl and ethyl esters were prepared.

A DAMS and co-workers¹ have prepared a variety of fatty acids. They have tested them for antileprosy effect. They found that a disubstituted acetic acid with a molecular weight between 250-280 had the most desirable physiological properties. Thus it was shown that the synthetically prepared compound I and II were found to possess as much physiological activity *in vitro* towards β -laprae as is possessed by mixed fatty acids obtained from chaulmoogra oil. They also found that in disubstituted acetic acids, the effect was more if a ω -cyclohexyl group is present in one of the alkyl groups. Thus the compound III was shown to possess more

than one and half a time the activity possessed by the best type of chaulmoogra oil—the oil from *Hydnocarpus wightiana*.

Various benzyl alkyl acetic acids² were prepared from ethyl benzyl malonate. The work has been extended by preparing *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetic acid from ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl malonate.

Malonic ester synthesis was adopted to prepare *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetic acid. *p*-Methoxy benzyl malonic ester (IV : R=H) was prepared from ethyl malonate and anisic chloride. It was converted into its sodio derivative by treatment with sodium in toluene. This was then reacted with *n*-heptyl bromide³. *p*-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonate (IV : R=C₇H₁₅n) thus obtained was purified by distillation and then hydrolysed to *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonic acid.

The latter on heating upto 130° was smoothly decarboxylated to give *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetic acid which was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. It has been characterised by preparation of various derivatives such as amide, anilide, *p*-toluidide, and methyl and ethyl esters.

Experimental

Ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl malonate : Ethyl malonate (82.0 g) was slowly added to finely divided sodium (11.5 g) in dry toluene (400 ml). After 2 hr the mixture was heated at 130° for about an hour and a half when all sodium dissolved. On cooling, anisic chloride (78 g) was slowly added in about 2 hr with constant shaking. The mixture was refluxed on the following day for about 2 hr. It was then cooled and decomposed by ice cold water. The oil separated, was washed with water and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Toluene was distilled over and the residual oil, ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl malonate distilled at 195°/15 mm., yield 105 g.

Analysis : Found C, 64.4 ; H, 7.1 ;

C₁₈H₂₀O₄ requires C, 64.4 ; H, 7.1 per cent.

Ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonate : Ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl malonate (70 g.) was slowly added to finely divided sodium (5.6 g.) in dry toluene (200 ml.). After about 2½ hr, it was heated on oil-bath for half an hour at 130°. On cooling *n*-heptyl iodide (56.5 g.) was gradually added in about 2 hr with constant shaking and cooling. The mixture was heated to 130° on the following day for about 2 hr. After cooling, it was decomposed with cold water. The oil separated, was washed with water and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Toluene

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was distilled over and ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonate was distilled at 230°-235°/15 mm., yield 96 g.

Analysis : Found C, 69.84 ; H, 8.99 ;

$C_{22}H_{34}O_6$ requires C, 69.82 ; H, 8.99 per cent.

p-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonic acid : Ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonate (80 g.) was heated with alcoholic potash (120 g. in 120 ml. H_2O and 120 ml ethanol) for 12 hr. After removing ethanol water was added to the mixture and was extracted with ether to remove neutral impurities. The alkaline solution was acidified and extracted with ether. After washing with sodium bicarbonate solution, ether solution was dried and ether removed. *p*-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonic acid (62 g.) was obtained as a viscous liquid. It could not be distilled without decomposition.

Analysis : Found C, 66.4 ; H, 7.92 ; Eq. wt. 158.2 :

$C_{18}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 67.08 ; H, 8.07 per cent.

p-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetic acid : On heating *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl malonic acid on an oil-bath at 150° for 1 hr, carbon dioxide was evolved and *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetic acid was obtained, b. p. 275°/18 mm, yield 51.0 g.

Analysis : Found C, 73.12 ; H, 9.34 ; Eq. wt. 277.3 ;

$C_{17}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 73.35 ; H, 9.35 per cent.

p-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride : *p*-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetic acid (40 g.) was heated on steam bath with thionyl chloride (60 g.) for about 1 hr. On removing the excess of thionyl chloride, *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride was obtained., b. p. 235°-237°/20 mm, yield 36.0 g.

Analysis : Found Cl, 11.61 ;

$C_{17}H_{26}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.98 per cent.

Methyl *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetate : It was obtained by refluxing *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride (10 g.) and methyl alcohol (50 ml.) for about half an hour and worked up in the usual manner. It had b. p. 245°/35 mm., yield 8.0 g.

Analysis : Found C, 73.92 ; H, 9.62 ;

$C_{18}H_{28}O_3$ requires C, 73.98 ; H, 9.6 per cent.

Ethyl *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetate : A mixture of *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride (10 g.) and absolute alcohol (50 ml.) was refluxed on

water bath for 1 hr. and worked up in the usual manner. It had b. p. 252°-255°/35 mm., yield 8.0 g.

Analysis : Found C, 74.3 ; H, 9.9 ;

$C_{19}H_{30}O_3$ requires C, 74.5 ; H, 9.8 per cent.

p-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetamide : *p*-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride (2 g.) was slowly added to ice cooled liquor ammonia (50 ml.) with constant stirring. *p*-Methoxy benzyl *n*-hexyl acetamide which separated was filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m. p. 122°, yield 1.6 g.

Analysis : Found C, 73.8 ; H, 9.64 ;

$C_{17}H_{27}O_2N$ requires C, 73.6 ; H, 9.75 per cent.

p-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetanilide : *p*-Methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride (2 g.) was heated with aniline (2 ml.) in dry benzene (10 ml.) for about half an hour. Benzene was removed and the residue was treated with diluted hydrochloric acid to remove unreacted aniline. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 102°-103°, yield 1.8 g.

Analysis : Found C, 78.0 ; H, 8.7 ;

$C_{28}H_{31}O_2N$ requires C, 78.18 ; H, 8.38 per cent.

p-Methoxy benzyl-*n*-heptyl acetyl *p*-toluidine : It was obtained as above by heating together *p*-methoxy benzyl *n*-heptyl acetyl chloride (2 g.) and *p*-toluidine (1.2 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml.). It was crystallised from dilute ethanol as small needles, m. p. 95°, yield 2.0 g.

Analysis : Found C, 78.25 ; H, 8.8 ;

$C_{24}H_{38}O_2N$ requires C, 78.47 ; H, 9.0 per cent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. S. Nargund, Hon. Professor of Chemistry, Parle College, Bombay-57, for his kind interest and valuable suggestions in the work and to Principal, Gujarat College, Ahmedabad for providing all the necessary facilities.

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